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CHETLARI SHARNIRLI MAHKAMLANGAN IKKI QATLAMLI QOVUSHOQ-ELASTIK PLASTINKANING KO‘NDALANG TEBRANISHLARI

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Аннотация. В данной работе рассматривается вопрос о выводе уравнений поперечных колебаний двухслойной вязкоупругой пластины. При этом использовались уточненные уравнения теории упругости. В результате получены приближенные уравнения поперечных колебаний двухслойной вязкоупругой пластины. Для проверки достоверности полученных уравнений из них были получены уравнения поперечных колебаний однородной пластины. Полученные уравнения сравнивают с уравнениями других авторов и получают необходимые результаты.

Ключевые слова: пластина, колебания, уравнения, слой, условия, перемещения

Annotation. In this paper, the question of the derivation of the equations of longitudinal vibrations of a two-layer viscoelastic plate is considered. In this case, refined equations of the theory of viscoelasticity were used. As a result, approximate equations of longitudinal vibrations of a two-layer viscoelastic plate are obtained. To verify the validity of the obtained equations, the equations of longitudinal vibrations of a homogeneous plate were obtained from them. The obtained equations are compared with the equations of other authors and the necessary results are obtained.

Keywords: plate, vibrations, equations, layer, conditions, displacements.

Kirish. Yurtimizda va xorijda texnikaning turli sohalarida fuqaro qurilishida qatlamli kompozit, jumladan, uch va ikki qatlamli plastinkalar keng qo‘llaniladi. Ko‘pgina hollarda bunday plastinkalarning dinamik hisobi Kirxgof gipotezalariga asoslangan klassik nazariyaga tayanilgan holda amalga oshiriladi. Ammo klassik nazariya uch va ikki qatlamli plastinkalarning kuchlanganlik-deformatsiyalanganlik holati komponentalarini to‘liq hisoblash imkonini bermaydi. Klassik nazariyaning qatlamli konstruksiyalar bo‘yicha rivoji S.G.Lexniskiy, E.Reysner, S.A.Ambarsumyan, I.G.Filippov, X.Xudoynazarov va boshqa bir qator olimlar tomonidan amalga oshirilmoqda. Qatlamli plastinkalarning dinamik hisobi nazariyalarini yaratish bo‘yicha tadqiqotlar ikkita yo‘nalishga bo‘linadi. Bulardan birinchisi asimtotiklik nazariya hamda Timoshenko va Reyssner tipidagi nazariyalarni ishlab chiqish ikkinchisi esa keyingi yillarda elastiklik nazariyasi uch o‘lchovli masalasining aniq yechimlaridan foydalanishga asoslangan nazariyalardir. Ikkinchi metod bilan professorlar G.I.Petrashen va I.G.Filippovlar, hamda ularning bir qator o‘quvchilari tomonidan qatlamli elastik va qovushoq-elastik plastinkalarning tebranishlari nazariyalari taklif etilgan [1-8]. Xususan ushbu usul bilan professor I.G.Filippov [6] va uning o‘quvchilari tomonidan simmetrik strukturaga ega bo‘lgan uch qatlamli plastinkalar tebranish nazariyalari yaratilgan.

Ushbu maqolada ikki qatlamli qovushoq-elastik plastinkaning taqribiy ko‘ndalang tebranish tenglamalari sistemasi qaralayotgan masala tekis masala deb qaralgan hol uchun keltirib chiqariladi.

Masalaning qo‘yilishi. Umumiy holda uch o‘lchovli fazoda o‘lchamlari cheksiz bo‘lgan ikki qatlamli elastik plastinkani qaraymiz. Bunday holda, plastinka qatlamlari bir jinsli va geometriyasi bir xil strukturali qovushoq-elastik materiallardan tashkil topgan, kuchlanishlar va deformatsiyalar orasida geometrik va fizik chiziqli bog‘lanishlar o‘rinli deb hisoblanadi. Plastinkani $Oxyz$ to‘g‘ri burchakli dekart koordinat sistemasiga joylashtiramiz (1-rasm). Bunda Ox va Oy o‘qlarni o‘zaro perpendikulyar ko‘ndalang kesimlarda, ularning o‘rta chiziqlari bo‘ylab yo‘naltiramiz, Oz – o‘qini esa yuqoriga, Oxy plastinka tekisligiga perpendikulyar yo‘naltiramiz [9-15]. Plastinka qatlamlarini xuddi 1-rasmdagidek raqamlab chiqamiz, ya‘ni yuqori qatlamni birinchi qatlam deb, quyi qatlamni – ikkinchi qatlam deb nomlaymiz.

Birinchi va ikkinchi qatlamlar qalinliklarini mos ravishda h_1 va h_2 lar orqali, qatlamlar materiallari uchun elastiklik modullarini, ya‘ni Lamé koeffisientlarini - λ_m, μ_m lar orqali; qatlamlar materiallarining zichliklarini ρ_m lar orqali belgilaymiz. Shuningdek qatlamlar ($m = 1,2$) nuqtalarining koordinat o‘qlari bo‘ylab ko‘chishlarini $U_m(x, y, z, t), V_m(x, y, z, t)$ va $W_m(x, y, z, t)$ orqali belgilaymiz.

1-rasm. Ikki qatlamli plastinka

Shu yerda va bundan keyingi hamma joyda m indeks doimo 1, 2 qiymatlarni qabul qiladi. Bu ko‘chishlar qovushoq-elastiklik chiziqli nazariyasida kichik ko‘chishlar deb hisoblanadi. Qatlamlar nuqtalarining kuchlanish va deformatsiya tenzorlari komponentalari uchun quyidagi hamma joyda qabul qilingan belgilashlarni ishlatamiz:

$\sigma_{xx}^{(m)}, \sigma_{yy}^{(m)}, \sigma_{zz}^{(m)}$ – normal va $\tau_{xy}^{(m)}, \tau_{yz}^{(m)}, \tau_{zx}^{(m)}$ – urinma kuchlanishlar; $\varepsilon_{xx}^{(m)}, \varepsilon_{yy}^{(m)}, \varepsilon_{zz}^{(m)}$ – normal, $\gamma_{xy}^{(m)}, \gamma_{yz}^{(m)}, \gamma_{zx}^{(m)}$ – burchak va $\varepsilon^{(m)} = \varepsilon_{xx}^{(m)} + \varepsilon_{yy}^{(m)} + \varepsilon_{zz}^{(m)}$ – hajmiy deformatsiya.

Plastinka qatlamlari nuqtalarida $\sigma_{ij}^{(m)} (i, j = 1,2,3; m = 0,1,2)$ kuchlanishlarning $\varepsilon_{ij}^{(m)} (i, j = 1,2,3; m = 0,1,2)$ deformatsiyalardan bog‘liqligi quyidagicha ifodalanadi

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma_{ii}^{(m)} &= \lambda_m(\varepsilon^{(m)}) + 2\mu_m(\varepsilon_{ii}^{(m)}); \\ \sigma_{ij}^{(m)} &= \mu_m(\varepsilon_{ij}^{(m)}); (i, j = 1, 2, 3; i \neq j), \\ \varepsilon^{(m)} &= \varepsilon_{xx}^{(m)} + \varepsilon_{yy}^{(m)} + \varepsilon_{zz}^{(m)}; (m = 0, 1)\end{aligned}\quad (1)$$

Plastinka qatlamlari nuqtalarining *Oxyz* dekart koordinatalaridagi harakat tenglamalari [9-11]

$$\sigma_{ij,j}^{(m)} = \rho_m \frac{\partial^2 \vec{U}^{(m)}}{\partial t^2}; (i, j = 1, 2, 3; m = 0, 1), \quad (2)$$

bu yyerda $\sigma_{ij}^{(m)}$ - kuchlanish tenzori komponentalari; ρ_m - qatlamlar materiallarining zichliklari; $\vec{U}^{(m)}$ - qatlam nuqtalarining ko'chish vektorlari; t - vaqt.

Quyidagi formulalar bo'yicha

$$\vec{U}^{(m)} = \text{grad } \varphi_m + \text{rot } \vec{\psi}_m, \quad (3)$$

$$\vec{U}^{(m)} = \vec{U}(U_m, V_m, W_m), \vec{\psi}_m = \vec{\psi}(\psi_{1m}, \psi_{2m}, \psi_{3m}), (m = 0, 1, 2)$$

skalyar φ_m va vektor $\vec{\psi}$ potentsiallarini kiritish bilan (2) munosabatlarni yetarlicha soddalashtirish mumkin [9-15]. Bunda $\vec{\psi}_m$ vektor potentsiallari vektor maydonlarining solenoidallik shartlarini qanoatlantiradilar

$$\text{div } \vec{\psi}_m = 0, (m = 0, 1) \quad (4)$$

Endi $\vec{U}^{(m)}$ ko'chish vektorlarining (3) ifodalarini (2) harakat tenglamalari sistemasiga qo'yib, plastinkaning qovushoq-elastik qatlamlari nuqtalarining harakat tenglamalarini bo'ylama φ_m va ko'ndalang $\vec{\psi}_m$ to'lqin potentsiallari orqali ifodalash qiyin emas

$$\lambda_{1m}(\Delta \varphi_m) = \rho_m \frac{\partial^2 \varphi_m}{\partial t^2}; \mu_m(\vec{\psi}_m) = \rho_m \frac{\partial^2 \vec{\psi}_m}{\partial t^2}; (m = 0, 1) \quad (5)$$

bu yerda ushbu belgilashlar kiritilgan

$$\lambda_{1m} = \lambda_m + 2\mu_m; \Delta = \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial y^2}.$$

Ko'chish vektorlari (3) ko'rinishida berilganda bunday vektorlarning komponentalari φ_m va ψ_m ($m = 1, 2$) potentsiallar orqali quyidagicha ifodalanadi

$$U_m = \frac{\partial \varphi_m}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial \psi_m}{\partial z}; W_m = \frac{\partial \varphi_m}{\partial z} + \frac{\partial \psi_m}{\partial x}, (m = 0, 1). \quad (6)$$

Xuddi shunga o'xshash, vektor maydonlarining (4) solenoidlik shartlarini dekart koordinatalari sistemasida yozish qiyin emas

$$\frac{\partial \varphi_m}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \psi_m}{\partial z} = 0, \quad (7)$$

Olingan (6) formulalar deformatsiyalar va kuchlanishlar tenzorlarining barcha komponentlarini kiritilgan potentsial funksiyalar orqali ifodalash imkonini beradi [9],

masalan

$$\varepsilon_{xx}^{(m)} = \frac{\partial^2 \varphi_m}{\partial x^2} - \frac{\partial^2 \psi_m}{\partial x \partial z}; \quad \varepsilon_{zz}^{(m)} = \frac{\partial^2 \varphi_m}{\partial z^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \psi_m}{\partial x \partial z}; \quad (8)$$

$$\varepsilon_{xz}^{(m)} = 2 \frac{\partial^2 \varphi_m}{\partial x \partial z} - \frac{\partial^2 \psi_m}{\partial z^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \psi_m}{\partial x^2}.$$

$$\sigma_{xx}^{(m)} = L_{1m}(\Delta \varphi_m) + 2M_m \left(\frac{\partial^2 \varphi_m}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \psi_{2m}}{\partial x \partial z} \right);$$

$$\sigma_{zz}^{(m)} = L_{1m}(\Delta \varphi_m) + 2M_m \left(\frac{\partial^2 \varphi_m}{\partial z^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \psi_m}{\partial x \partial z} \right); \quad (9)$$

$$\tau_{xz}^{(m)} = M_m \left(2 \frac{\partial^2 \varphi_m}{\partial x \partial z} - \frac{\partial^2 \psi_m}{\partial z^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \psi_m}{\partial x^2} \right).$$

Vaqtning $t < 0$ bo‘lgan qiymatlarida plastinka tinch (muvozanat) holatida, $t = 0$ paytda esa qalinlik bo‘yicha koordinataning $z = \pm h_i^*$; $h_i^* = h_0 + h_i$, ($i = 1, 2$) qiymatlarida, yoki uning chegaraviy tekisliklariga dinamik kuchlar ta‘sir etadi deb faraz qilinadi. Boshqacha aytganda chegaraviy shartlar quyidagi ko‘rinishda berilgan deb hisoblanadi [9,13],

$$\tau_{xz}^{(i)}(x, y, z, t) \Big|_{z=\pm h_i^*} = \pm F_{xz}^{(i)}(x, y, t);$$

$$\sigma_{zz}^{(i)}(x, y, z, t) \Big|_{z=\pm h_i^*} = \pm F_z^{(i)}(x, y, t); \quad (10)$$

$$\tau_{xz}^{(i)}(x, y, z, t) \Big|_{z=\pm h_i^*} = 0.$$

Yuqoridagi plastinka $t < 0$ bo‘lganda tinch holatda bo‘lgan deb qabul qilingan mulohazaga ko‘ra barcha qatlamlar tinch holatda joylashgan deb hisoblaymiz, bu esa $t = 0$ da boshlang‘ich shartlar nolga tengligini ko‘rsadi va ularni potensial funksiyalar orqali quyidagicha yozamiz:

$$\varphi_m = \psi_{km} = \frac{\partial \varphi_m}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial \psi_{km}}{\partial t} = 0, \quad (m = 1, 2). \quad (11)$$

Chegaraviy (10) shartlardan tashqari, plastinkaning yuqori qatlami bilan quyi qatlami kontakt tekisliklarida quyidagi dinamik va kinematik kontakt shartlar o‘rinli [9]:

$$\sigma_{zz}^{(1)} = \sigma_{zz}^{(2)}; \quad \tau_{xz}^{(1)} = \tau_{xz}^{(2)}; \quad \tau_{xz}^{(1)} = \tau_{xz}^{(2)}; \quad (12)$$

$$U_1 = U_2; \quad V_1 = V_2; \quad W_1 = W_2.$$

Ta‘kidlash kerakki, (11) potentsiallar uchun boshlang‘ich shartlar $t = 0$ da U_m, V_m, W_m ($m = 0, 1, 2$) ko‘chishlar komponentalari uchun shakllantirilgan boshlang‘ich shartlarga teng kuchli, ya‘ni:

$$U_m = V_m = W_m = 0; \quad \frac{\partial U_m}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial V_m}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial W_m}{\partial t} = 0. \quad (13)$$

Shunday qilib, ikki qatlamli plastinkaning ko‘ndalang tebranishlari haqidagi

masalaning qo‘yilishida masala har bir qatlam uchun (10) – chegaraviy, (12) – kontakt hamda (11) yoki (13) – nol boshlang‘ich shartlarda (5) tenglamalarni yechishga keltiriladi.

Masalaning yechimi. Shunday qilib ikki qatlamli plastinkaning ko‘ndalang tebranishlari haqidagi masalani yechish uchun (5) tenglamalarni (10)–chegaraviy, (12)– kontakt hamda (11) yoki (13) – nolovoy boshlang‘ich shartlarda yechamiz. Qo‘yilgan masalani yechish uchun plastinka sirtlariga qo‘yilgan tashqi ta‘sir funksiyalari uchun ifodalarni ya‘ni $f_x^{(1,2)}(x, t)$ va $f_z^{(1,2)}(x, t)$ funksiyalarning ko‘rinishlarini keltirish zarur. Bu funksiyalarning ko‘rinishlarini aniqlashda ularga qo‘yilgan shartlarni hisobga olgan holda bu funksiyalarni quyidagi ko‘rinishda tasvirlaymiz, ya‘ni [12]

$$\begin{aligned} f_x^{(1,2)}(x, t) &= \int_0^\infty \left. \begin{matrix} \sin kx \\ -\cos kx \end{matrix} \right\} dk \int_{(l)}^{\square} \tilde{f}_x^{(1,2)}(k, p) e^{pt} dp; \\ f_z^{(1,2)}(x, t) &= \int_0^\infty \left. \begin{matrix} \cos kx \\ \sin kx \end{matrix} \right\} dk \int_{(l)}^{\square} \tilde{f}_z^{(1,2)}(k, p) e^{pt} dp; \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

Tashqi ta‘sir funksiyalarining qabul qilingan tasvirlariga mos ravishda yuqorida shakllantirilgan (5), (10), (11), (12), (13) va (14) masalaning yechimini ham quyidagi ko‘rinishda izlaymiz

$$\begin{aligned} \varphi_m(x, z, t) &= \int_0^\infty \left. \begin{matrix} \sin kx \\ -\cos kx \end{matrix} \right\} dk \int_{(l)}^{\square} \tilde{\varphi}_m(k, z, p) e^{pt} dp; \\ \psi_m(x, z, t) &= \int_0^\infty \left. \begin{matrix} \cos kx \\ \sin kx \end{matrix} \right\} dk \int_{(l)}^{\square} \tilde{\psi}_m(k, z, p) e^{pt} dp, \quad (m = 1, 2). \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

Potensial funksiyalarning ushbu tasvirlarini (5) tenglamalar sistemasiga qo‘ysak, Besselning ikkinchi tartibli oddiy differensial tenglamalariga kelamiz

$$\frac{\partial^2 \tilde{\varphi}_m}{\partial z^2} - \alpha_m^2 \tilde{\varphi}_m = 0; \quad \frac{\partial^2 \tilde{\psi}_m}{\partial z^2} - \beta_m^2 \tilde{\psi}_m = 0; \quad (m = 0, 1) \quad (16)$$

bu yerda

$$\alpha_m^2 = k^2 + \rho_m p^2 \tilde{\lambda}_{1m}^{-1}; \quad \beta_m^2 = k^2 + \rho_m p^2 \tilde{\mu}_m^{-1}; \quad \tilde{\lambda}_{1m} = (\tilde{\lambda}_m + 2\tilde{\mu}_m). \quad (17)$$

Olingan (16) tenglamalarning umumiy yechimlarini giperbolik trigonometrik funksiyalar kombinatsiyalari ko‘rinishida olamiz

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\varphi}_m(k, z, p) &= A_m^{(1)}(k, p) ch(\alpha_m z) + A_m^{(2)}(k, p) sh(\alpha_m z); \\ \tilde{\psi}_m(k, z, p) &= B_m^{(1)}(k, p) sh(\beta_m z) + B_m^{(2)}(k, p) ch(\beta_m z); \quad (m = 0, 1, 2) \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

Plastinkaning simmetrik tebranishlarini tashqi simmetrik ta‘sirlar paydo qiladi.

Shuning uchun ushbu yechimlar simmetrik tebranishlarni tavsif etishlari uchun $A_m^{(1)} = 0, B_m^{(1)} = 0, (m = 0,1,2)$ tengliklar bajarilishini taqozo qiladi. U holda plastinkaning ko‘ndalang (antisimmetrik) tebranishlari holida (18) umumiy yechimlar quyidagi ko‘rinishga ega bo‘ladilar.

$$\begin{aligned}\tilde{\varphi}_m(k, z, p) &= A_m^{(2)}(k, p)sh(\alpha_m z); \\ \tilde{\psi}_m(k, z, p) &= B_m^{(2)}(k, p)ch(\beta_m z); (m = 0,1,2)\end{aligned}\quad (19)$$

(19) yechimdan foydalanib kuchlanishlar ifodalarini ham ular orqali ifodalab chegaraviy shartlardan foydalanib [15], ikki izlanuvchi funksiyalarga nisbatan ikki qatlamli qovushoq-elastik plastinkaning amaliy masalalarni yechishda qo‘llash mumkin bo‘lgan bo‘ylama tebranish tenglamalari sistemasini hosil qilamiz:

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{(1+h_1)h_0^2}{l^2}\left(\frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2}-\frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2}\right)\frac{\partial^2 W_0^{(0)}}{\partial t^2}-\frac{h_0^2}{6\xi l^2}\left\{\left[2-\frac{b_0^2}{a_0^2}\right]\frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2}+(1+2q_0)\frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2}+\frac{6l_0^2}{h_0^2}\right\}\frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2}+8q_1(1+h_1)^2\frac{\partial^4}{\partial x^4}\left\}\frac{\partial U_0^{(0)}}{\partial x}=\\ =\frac{\partial^2 f_1^{(2)}}{\partial t^2}+\frac{4h_0^2 b_1^2}{3l^2 b_0^2}q_1(1+h_1)^3\frac{\partial^4 f_1^{(1)}}{\partial x^4}+(1+h_1)\frac{\partial^2 f_1^{(1)}}{\partial t^2}, \\ \frac{(1+h_2)h_0^2}{l^2}\left\{\left[(1-2q_0)\left(\frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2}-\frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2}\right)+\frac{2l^2}{h_0^2}\right]\frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2}+\frac{8b_2^2 q_2(1+h_2)^2}{3b_0^2}\frac{\partial^4}{\partial x^4}\right\}\frac{\partial W_0^{(0)}}{\partial x}+ \\ +\frac{1}{2\xi}\left\{\left[\frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2}-(1-2q_0)\frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2}+\frac{2l^2}{h_0^2}\right]\frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2}+\frac{8b_2^2 q_2(1+h_2)^2}{3b_0^2}\frac{\partial^4}{\partial x^4}\right\}U_0^{(0)}= \\ =\frac{2l}{h_0}(1+h_2)\frac{\partial^2 f_2^{(2)}}{\partial t^2}+q_2 h_2(2+h_2)\left(\frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2}-\frac{b_2^2}{b_0^2}\frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2}\right)\frac{\partial f_1^{(2)}}{\partial x},\end{aligned}\quad (20)$$

Xususiyl holda (20) tenglamalar sistemasida $h_2 = 0$ deb olsak bir jinsli plastinka tebranish tenglamasi kelib chiqadi.

$$\begin{aligned}\Delta_2 M_0\left\{\left[1+\frac{1}{2b_0^2}(1-2q_0)h_0^2\frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2}-\frac{1}{2}h_0^2(1-2q_0)\frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2}\right]\frac{\partial}{\partial x}W_0^{(0)}+\frac{1}{\xi}\left[1+\frac{1}{2b_0^2}h_0^2\frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2}-\frac{1}{2}h_0^2(1+2q_0)\frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2}\right]U_0^{(0)}\right\}=f_x^{(2)} \\ \Delta_1 M_0 h_0\left\{\left[\frac{1}{6a_0^2 b_0^2}h_0^2\frac{\partial^4}{\partial t^4}-\frac{1}{6}h_0^2\left(\frac{1}{a_0^2}+\frac{1}{b_0^2}(1-2q_0)\right)\frac{\partial^4}{\partial t^2 \partial x^2}+\frac{1}{6}h_0^2(1-2q_0)\frac{\partial^4}{\partial x^4}+\frac{1}{b_0^2}\frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2}-\frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2}\right]W_0^{(0)}+ \\ +\frac{1}{\xi}\left[\frac{1}{6}h_0^2\left(\frac{1}{a_0^2}-\frac{2}{b_0^2}\right)\frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2}-\frac{1}{6}h_0^2(1+2q_0)\frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2}-1\right]\frac{\partial}{\partial x}U_0^{(0)}\right\}=f_z^{(1)}\end{aligned}\quad (21)$$

Olingan natijalar. Olingan tebranish tenglamalarini qiyosiy tahlil qilish uchun G.I.Petrashen va E.V.Xinen tomonidan olingan bir jinsli elastik plastinkaning tebranish tenglamalarini keltiramiz.

$$2\frac{\partial \chi_0}{\partial x}+\left(2\frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2}-\frac{1}{b_0^2}\frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2}\right)\zeta_0+\frac{h_0^2}{2}\left[2\left(\frac{1}{a_0^2}\frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2}-\frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2}\right)\frac{\partial \chi_0}{\partial x}+\right.$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & + \left(2 \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} - \frac{1}{b_0^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} \right) \left(\frac{1}{b_0^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} - \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} \right) \zeta_0 \Big] = \frac{1}{\mu_0} f_x^+(x, t), \quad (22) \\
 & \left(\frac{1}{b^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} - 2 \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} \right) \chi_0 + 2 \left(\frac{1}{b^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} - \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} \right) \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \zeta_0 + \\
 & + \frac{h^2}{6} \left[\left(\frac{1}{b^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} - 2 \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} \right) \left(\frac{1}{a^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} - \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} \right) \chi_0 + 2 \left(\frac{1}{b^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} - \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} \right)^2 \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \zeta_0 \right] = \frac{1}{\mu_0} \frac{f_z^+(x, t)}{h}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Bu yerda χ va ζ – quyidagi formulalar bilan aniqlanadigan plastinka nuqtalari ko'ndalang va bo'ylama ko'chishlarning bosh qismlari.

(21) va (22) tenglamalar sistemasini sonli natijalarini qiyosiy tahlil qilish uchun plastinkaning fizik-mexanik va geometrik parametrlarini hamda tashqi kuchlarning quyidagi qiymatlari bilan hal qilindi, ular doimiy deb faraz qilinadi:

Plastinka uzunligi $l = 1 \text{ m}$, plastinka qalinligi $h = 0.1 \text{ m}$, plastinka zichligi $\rho = 2700 \text{ kg/m}^3$, plastinka materiali uchun Yung moduli $E_0 = E = 7 \cdot 10^{10} \text{ Pa}$, plastinka materiali uchun Puasson koeffitsiyenti $\nu_0 = \nu = 0.34$, plastinka qatlamidan tanlangan sirt bilan plastinka o'rta sirtigacha bo'lgan masofa $\xi = 0.3h_1$, plastinka tashqi sirtlariga ta'sir qiluvchi kuchlar $f_x = 0$; $f_z = 8 \text{ MPa}$.

Bu ikki nazariyaga ko'ra olingan sonli natijalar bo'ylama va ko'ndalang ko'chishlar grafiklari ko'rinishida 2-va 3-rasmlarda ko'rsatilgan. Vaqtni noldan birga o'zgartirganda (2- va 3-rasmlar) $x = 0.5$ kesim nutasining ko'chishi shuningdek, x koordinatasini noldan birga o'zgartirganda (4- va 5-rasmlar) $t = 0.6$ da o'rta kesim nuqtasining ko'chishlari uchun hisob-kitob ishlari amalga oshirildi.

— un — u
 — Petrashen nazariyasi
 — Taklif qilinayotgan nazariya
2-rasm. $x = 0.5$; $0 \leq t \leq 1$ da turli nazariyalarga ko'ra U bo'ylama ko'chish qiymatlarini taqqoslash.

— wn — w
 — Petrashen nazariyasi
 — Taklif qilinayotgan nazariya
3-rasm. $x = 0.5$; $0 \leq t \leq 1$ da turli nazariyalarga ko'ra W ko'ndalang ko'chish qiymatlarini taqqoslash.

— Petraschen nazariyasi

— Taklif qilinayotgan nazariya

4-rasm. $t = 0.6$; $0 \leq x \leq 1$ da turli nazariyalarga ko'ra U bo'ylama ko'chish qiymatlarini taqqoslash.

— Petraschen nazariyasi

— Taklif qilinayotgan nazariya

5-rasm. $t = 0.6$; $0 \leq x \leq 1$ da turli nazariyalarga ko'ra W ko'ndalang ko'chish qiymatlarini taqqoslash.

Xulosa. Ushbu nazariyalarga muvofiq ko'chishlarning keltirilgan grafiklaridan kelib chiqqan holda, ular deyarli to'liq mos keladi. Bu bir qatlamli holatda G.I.Petraschen va E.V.Xinenning taniqli nazariyasiga to'liq mos keladigan uch qatlamli plastinkaning simmetrik tebranishlari nazariyasini ishlab chiqish metodologiyasining to'g'riligini isbotlaydi. Hisoblash natijalarining mos kelishi ham olingan natijalarning ishonchligining isboti bo'lib xizmat qiladi.

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